

10. AMPARO NOSTRALIS and LUZOLIVEROS, *Belarado Rav. Filipina Medform*, 1941, **32**, p. 62 (C.A. 1941, **35**, 4916).
11. OTTO RICHARD GOTTLIEB and MAURO, *Taveira Magathães Anais Assoc. Brazil*, Quim 1959, **18**, p. 179 (C.A. 1969, **54**, 11386^b).
12. Elvira Fermin Silva, *Proc. Pacific Sci. Congress, Pacific Sci. Assoc, 8th Quezonaty*, 1953, **4A**, p. 148, Pub. 1954 (C.A. 1961, **55**, 4890^b).
13. V. K. DIXIT, K. C. VARMA and V. N. VASHISHT '*Indian J. Pharm.*' 1977, **39**, p. 58 (C.A. 1977, **87**, 106642^x).
13. S. C. SHARMA, C. SHUKLA and J. S. TANDON '*Phytochemistry*', 1975, **14**, 1059 (C.A. 1975, **83**, 53419^p).
2. L. JURD and R. M. HOROWITZ, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1956, **21**, 1395.
3. L. JURD and R. M. HOROWITZ, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1958, **22**, 1618.
4. E. T. JONES and A. ROBERTSON, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1933, 1167.

N-Acridin-5-yl-N'-Aryloxyacetyl Hydrazines as Possible Fungicides

(MISS) U. SRIVASTAVA, (MISS) B. JAHAN

and

S. C. BAHEL

Chemistry Department, University of Gorakhpur,
Gorakhpur-273 001, U. P.

Manuscript received 6 March 1979, accepted 4 August 1979

Chemical Examination of the Seeds of

Cassia laevigata

R. D. TIWARI and ANJALI RICHARDS

Chemistry Department, Allahabad University,
Allahabad-211 002

*Manuscript received 27 February 1978,
accepted 4 August 1979*

FROM the hot ethanolic extract of the seeds of *Cassia laevigata* two anthraquinones, chrysophanol (I) and physcion(II) and a flavonoid, quercetin 3,7-di-rhamnopyranoside(III) have been isolated and studied.

Compound (I), m.p. 195°, $C_{15}H_{10}O_4$, has been shown to be 1,8-di-hydroxy-3-methyl-anthraquinone (chrysophanol) and compound (II) m.p. 207°, $C_{15}H_{12}O_5$ characterised as 1,8-di-hydroxy-6-methoxy-3-methyl-anthraquinone (physcion), by analysis, colour reactions, spectral data, degradation studies and derivatization.

The third compound m.p. 190° (d), $C_{27}H_{20}O_{17}$, on hydrolysis gave quercetin ($C_{15}H_{10}O_7$) and rhamnose. The position of the rhamnose units have been shown to be with the 3- and 7-hydroxyls by colour reactions¹ and spectral shift^{2,3}. The rhamnose units are present in the pyranose form as proved by periodate oxidation⁴ and the glycosidic linkages as α -, confirmed by its hydrolysis with takadiastase.

All the three compounds are known to occur in plants particularly in the genus *Cassia*.

Acknowledgement

One of us (A.R.) expresses her grateful thanks to CSIR for a Senior Research Fellowship.

References

1. M. SHIMZU, *J. Pharm. Soc.*, (Japan), 1951, **71**, 1339.

ALTHOUGH an unsubstituted nucleus containing heterocyclic nitrogen is seldom fungitoxic, acridine is known to be toxic to spores of various rusts¹. Horsfall and Rich² found acridine to be fairly active against *Sclerotinia fructicola* and *Macrosporium sarcinaeforme*. Acridines have been found to act as insecticides³⁻⁵, fungicides^{2,6}, bactericides⁷, medicinals⁸ and carcinogenic⁹ compounds.

We have therefore synthesised N-acridin-5-yl-N'-aryloxyacetyl hydrazines and screened some of them for their fungicidal activity against *A. flavus* and *H. oryzae*.

Experimental

All melting points are uncorrected.

N-Acridin-5-yl-N'-aryloxyacetyl hydrazines(I) :

A methanolic solution of a substituted-5-chloro-acridine¹⁰ (0.002 M) and an aryloxy acetyl hydrazine¹¹ (0.002 M) was refluxed gently for three hrs and cooled. The product separating out was filtered and recrystallised.

The compounds thus prepared, have been listed in Table 1.

Fungicidal Activity :

Twenty-one of these compounds were screened for their antifungal activity against *A. flavus* and *H. oryzae* by agar plate technique¹² and found to be moderately active. The most active compounds were found to contain a naphthoxy ring. A change in the position of ethoxy group did not show any effect towards antifungal activity. Halogenated compounds possessed a bit higher fungicidal activity.

TABLE I—N-ACRIDIN-5-YL-N'-ARYLOXYACETYL HYDRAZINES

Sl. No.	R	R ₁	M.P. °C	Yield %	Molecular formula	Found N%	Calcd.
*1.	<i>o</i> -Chlorophenyl	H	225	85.1	C ₂₁ H ₁₆ ClN ₂ O ₂	11.01	11.12
*2.	<i>o</i> -Chlorophenyl	3-Cl	258	93.5	C ₂₂ H ₁₅ Cl ₂ N ₂ O ₂	10.01	10.19
*3.	<i>o</i> -Chlorophenyl	1-Cl	185	96.7	C ₂₁ H ₁₅ Cl ₂ N ₂ O ₂	10.02	10.19
4.	<i>o</i> -Chlorophenyl	1- <i>o</i> Me	236	83.3	C ₂₂ H ₁₆ ClN ₂ O ₂	10.15	10.30
5.	<i>o</i> -Chlorophenyl	1-Me	216	86.2	C ₂₂ H ₁₆ ClN ₂ O ₂	10.58	10.72
6.	<i>o</i> -Chlorophenyl	3-Br	240	86.7	C ₂₂ H ₁₅ BrClN ₂ O ₂	9.01	9.24
*7. ^a	<i>o</i> -Tolyl	H	216	75.8	C ₂₂ H ₁₆ N ₂ O ₂	11.61	11.76
*8.	<i>o</i> -Tolyl	3-Cl	203	83.3	C ₂₃ H ₁₆ ClN ₂ O ₂	10.61	10.72
*9.	<i>o</i> -Tolyl	1-Cl	105	85.1	C ₂₂ H ₁₆ ClN ₂ O ₂	10.59	10.72
*10.	<i>o</i> -Tolyl	1-Me	240	81.1	C ₂₃ H ₁₇ N ₂ O ₂	11.22	11.32
11.	<i>o</i> -Tolyl	1- <i>o</i> Me	220	78.9	C ₂₃ H ₁₇ N ₂ O ₂	10.76	10.85
*12.	<i>o</i> -Tolyl	3-Br	183	88.3	C ₂₃ H ₁₆ BrN ₂ O ₂	9.84	9.63
13. ^b	<i>m</i> -Tolyl	H	186	75.8	C ₂₂ H ₁₆ N ₂ O ₂	11.62	11.76
*14.	<i>m</i> -Tolyl	3-Cl	154	83.3	C ₂₃ H ₁₆ ClN ₂ O ₂	10.56	10.72
*15.	<i>m</i> -Tolyl	1-Cl	105	85.1	C ₂₂ H ₁₆ ClN ₂ O ₂	10.62	10.72
16.	<i>m</i> -Tolyl	1-Me	221	81.1	C ₂₃ H ₁₇ N ₂ O ₂	11.18	11.32
17.	<i>m</i> -Tolyl	1- <i>o</i> Me	197	78.9	C ₂₃ H ₁₇ N ₂ O ₂	10.73	10.85
*18.	<i>m</i> -Tolyl	3-Br	197	88.3	C ₂₃ H ₁₆ BrN ₂ O ₂	9.52	9.63
*19. ^c	α -Naphthyl	H	217	77.9	C ₂₂ H ₁₆ N ₂ O ₂	8.76	8.90
*20.	β -Naphthyl	H	149	90.0	C ₂₂ H ₁₆ N ₂ O ₂	8.81	8.90
21.	α -Naphthyl	1-Cl	280	59.0	C ₂₃ H ₁₅ ClN ₂ O ₂	9.68	9.82
22.	β -Naphthyl	1-Cl	280	71.0	C ₂₃ H ₁₅ ClN ₂ O ₂	9.65	9.82
23.	α -Naphthyl	3-Cl	102	47.5	C ₂₃ H ₁₅ ClN ₂ O ₂	9.70	9.82
24.	β -Naphthyl	3-Cl	283	71.2	C ₂₃ H ₁₅ ClN ₂ O ₂	9.71	9.82
*25.	α -Naphthyl	1-Me	222	86.4	C ₂₃ H ₁₆ N ₂ O ₂	10.21	10.32
*26.	β -Naphthyl	1-Me	280	61.7	C ₂₃ H ₁₆ N ₂ O ₂	10.18	10.32
27.	α -Naphthyl	3-Me	209	72.4	C ₂₃ H ₁₆ N ₂ O ₂	10.14	10.32
28. ^d	β -Naphthyl	3-Me	280	61.0	C ₂₃ H ₁₆ N ₂ O ₂	10.22	10.32
29.	α -Naphthyl	1- <i>o</i> Me	150	71.4	C ₂₄ H ₁₇ N ₂ O ₂	10.08	9.93
30.	β -Naphthyl	1- <i>o</i> Me	265	71.0	C ₂₄ H ₁₇ N ₂ O ₂	9.72	9.93
31.	α -Naphthyl	3- <i>o</i> Me	267	71.4	C ₂₄ H ₁₇ N ₂ O ₂	9.75	9.93
32.	β -Naphthyl	3- <i>o</i> Me	227	71.4	C ₂₄ H ₁₇ N ₂ O ₂	9.79	9.93
*33.	α -Naphthyl	3-Br	206	31.9	C ₂₃ H ₁₅ BrN ₂ O ₂	8.76	8.90
*34.	β -Naphthyl	3-Br	230	42.5	C ₂₃ H ₁₅ BrN ₂ O ₂	8.79	8.90
*35.	α -Naphthyl	1-OEt	189	36.0	C ₂₄ H ₁₇ N ₂ O ₂	9.51	9.61
*36.	β -Naphthyl	1-OEt	169	36.6	C ₂₄ H ₁₇ N ₂ O ₂	9.48	9.61
*37.	α -Naphthyl	3-OEt	240	40.0	C ₂₄ H ₁₇ N ₂ O ₂	9.51	9.61
*38.	β -Naphthyl	3-OEt	260	48.3	C ₂₄ H ₁₇ N ₂ O ₂	9.46	9.61

* Compounds screened for antifungal activity.

Significant bands (cm⁻¹) in IR spectra (in KBr disc)

Secondary N-H	<i>o</i> -Disubstituted benzene	Conjugated cyclic C=N
a. 3320	a. 750	a. 1600
b. 3280	<i>m</i> -Disubstituted benzene	b. 1620
	b. 750	
c. 3300		c. 1610
d. 3270		d. 1625

Acknowledgement

Authors sincerely thank Prof. R. P. Rastogi, Head, Chemistry Department, University of Gorakhpur, Gorakhpur, for departmental facilities. One of us (U. S.) is grateful to UGC, New Delhi for the award of JRF.

References

1. STRAIB, ZENTRAL, *Bakt. Abst.*, 1941, 2, 103.
2. J. G. HORSFALL and S. RICH, *Boyce Thomson Institute*, 1951, 16, 316.
3. W. D. STEWART and J. H. STANDEN, *Chem. Abstr.*, 1950, 41, 8591b.
4. K. C. JOSHI and M. K. THOLIA, *Agr. Biol. Chem.*, 1974, 38, 1165.
5. K. C. JOSHI and S. C. BAHREL, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1961, 38, 877.
6. R. H. KHAN and S. C. BAHREL, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1976, 53, 837.

7. NG. PH. BUU-HOI and P. JACQUINGTON, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1952, 4173.
8. J. H. WILKINSON and I. L. FINAR, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1947, 759, 1948, 288.
9. R. M. BRADLOW and C. A. VANDERWERF, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1948, 70, 654.
10. *Organic Syntheses, Vol. 3*, p. 53, John Wiley and Sons, Inc. N. Y. 1955.
11. M. L. TAMAYO, G. ALONSO and R. MADROHERO, *Chem. Abs.*, 1962, 57, 9834 d.
12. U.S.D.A., *Circular No. 198*, 1931.

**Chemical Constituents of *Gmelina philippinensis*,
Adenocalymna nitida, *Allamanda cathartica*,
Averrhoa carambola and *Maba buxifolia***

K. P. TIWARI, M. MASOOD and P. K. MINOCHA

Department of Chemistry, University of Allahabad, Allahabad

*Manuscript received 7 July 1978, revised 16 March 1979,
accepted 4 August 1979*

GMELINA *philippinensis* (N. O. Verbenaceae), *Adenocalymna nitida* (N. O. Bignoniaceae), *Allamanda cathartica* (N. O. Apocyanaceae) and *Averrhoa carambola* (N. O. Oxalidaceae) are very often cultivated in Indian gardens. Some of them find extensive medicinal uses for the treatment of various ailments^{1,2}. The presence of kaempferol and quercetin from the flowers of *A. cathartica* has already been reported³.

The air dried flowers (1 kg each) of *G. philippinensis*, *A. nitida*, *A. cathartica* and *A. carambola* were extracted exhaustively with ethanol separately. The ethanolic extracts were concentrated and they were extracted with petroleum ether to remove oil and fats. The concentrated extracts left after the extraction with petroleum ether were extracted with acetone. The acetone extracts were concentrated and adsorbed onto the column of magnesol⁴. On eluting with ethyl acetate saturated with water kaempferol, C₁₅H₁₀O₆, m.p. 276-8°(d) has been obtained from *G. philippinensis*, *A. nitida* and *A. cathartica*, quercetin, C₁₅H₁₀O₇, m.p. 316°(d) and hesperitin C₁₆H₁₀O₈, m.p. 220-2°(d) were obtained from *A. nitida* and *A. cathartica* and quercetin-3-O-β-D-glucoside, C₂₁H₂₀O₁₂, m.p. 234-6° and rutin, C₂₇H₃₀O₁₆, m.p. 188° were obtained from *A. carambola*. The glycosides were characterised by the spectral studies and studies of their hydrolysis products.

Previous studies have shown the presence of 7, 9, 9 trimethyl hexa cosan-8 one, friedelin, friedelin-3-ol, oleanolic acid, quercetin, taxifolin and taxifolin-7-O-α-L galactopyranoside from the stem of *M. buxifolia*⁵.

The air dried, powdered and defatted leaves (3 kg) of *M. buxifolia* were extracted exhaustively with ethanol. The ethanolic extract was concentrated to a thick viscous mass. The thick viscous mass

was taken in water (1 litre) and was shaken vigorously. The water insoluble substances were separated by filtration. The filtrate on concentration gave a thick brown syrupy substance which was found to be flavonoid glycoside. The study of syrupy flavonoid glycoside is in progress.

The water insoluble fraction was extracted exhaustively with hexane to remove chlorophyll and fat. The water insoluble fraction, left after the removal of chlorophyll and fat was extracted with chloroform (4 × 100 ml). The chloroform insoluble substance was recrystallised from hot ethanol, m.p. 102° which could not be studied due to paucity of the material. The chloroform extract was concentrated and passed through a column of silica gel using mixture of benzene and chloroform (1 : 1) as solvent whereupon friedelin, C₃₀H₅₀O, m.p. 265° and friedelin-3-ol C₃₀H₅₂O, m.p. 281-2° were obtained.

Acknowledgement

The authors are very grateful to Drs. D. S. Bhakuni (CDRI, Lucknow), T. R. Govindachari, R. S. Grewal, S. Selvavinayakam (CIBA-GEIGY Research Centre, Bombay) for providing spectral data of the compounds reported in this paper.

References

1. R. N. CHOPRA, S. L. NAYAR and I. C. CHOPRA, 'Glossary of Indian Medicinal Plants', C.S.I.B., New Delhi Publication, 1956, p. 11 and 81.
2. L. H. BAILLY, *The Standard Cyclopedia of Horticulture*, Macmillan Co., New York, Vol. I, 215.
3. S. SANKARA SUBRAMANIAN and M. M. SWAMY, *Curr. Sci.*, 1963, 32, 308.
4. C. H. ICE and S. H. WENDER, *Anal. Chem.*, 1952, 240, 1616.
5. Y. K. S. RATHORE, D. Phil. Thesis, University of Allahabad, 1977.

The Correlation between Carbonyl Stretching Frequencies, Force Constant and Formal Bond Order in Carbonyl Complexes

K. GOSWAMI and M. M. SINGH*

Department of Chemistry, Dibrugarh University
Dibrugarh 786 004, Assam

Manuscript received 4 August 1978, accepted 13 July 1979

A large number of carbonyl complexes of transition metals have been prepared and studied. Of all the physical methods of their investigations, the use of i.r. method with special reference to carbonyl bands is the most informative. The shifts of carbonyl stretching frequencies and their intensities have been explained on the basis of involvement of metal d_π or p_z orbitals in π-bonding with CO and